

A Sneak Peek into AI-Generated 3D Immersive Memories

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Figure 1: User-friendly process for generating 3D personal objects. Users describe and capture their objects through text or audio and through images or video. These inputs are processed to generate four 3D versions of the same object using three Diffusion Models (Text-to-3D, Image-to-3D and Gaussian Splatting). These versions are then evaluated by participants in terms of realism, aesthetics, resemblance and reminiscence of the original object, and overall preference.

Abstract

Creating immersive content using generative AI is a likely future. In this paper, we take a sneak peek into that future. We collaborated with sixteen users to create their memories with them. Different

methods, including three generative AI pipelines and Gaussian Splatting, were used to recreate twelve personal objects. Twelve participants were instructed to select one version and subjectively assess each 3D reconstruction in four dimensions: realism, aesthetics, resemblance, and reminiscence. Our results show that Gaussian Splatting is generally preferred for its fidelity, while image-to-3D pipelines are competitive on aesthetic appeal. Crucially, reminiscence, how well a reconstruction evokes the original memory, emerged as the strongest driver of preference, suggesting that for this group emotional resonance matters more than visual realism.

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CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → **Shape representations**; *Computer vision*; • **Human-centered computing** → *Empirical studies in HCI*.

Keywords

Generative AI, Immersive Media, 3D reconstruction, User study, Co-creation, Digital heritage

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1 Introduction

Immersive media such as Extended Reality (XR) provide forms of presence and engagement beyond traditional screen-based media [16]. However, the production of immersive content remains a major barrier to adoption, as creating 3D assets is still resource-intensive and requires specialised hardware and expertise.

Recent advances are reducing this barrier. Techniques such as 3D Gaussian Splatting (GS) [7] enable photorealistic capture from standard video, while generative AI models can produce 3D content from images [12, 25], video [27], or text [26]. These developments indicate a shift towards more accessible immersive content creation, allowing non-experts to generate 3D content using everyday devices like phone cameras or by providing verbal descriptions. Communities lacking specialised resources now possess greater opportunities to create and share their own immersive experiences.

In this work-in-progress paper, we explore how such emerging 3D reconstruction pipelines may support accessible and participatory immersive content creation in a memory-driven context. As part of the Horizon Europe project AMPLIFY, we collaborate with women over 70 years of age who were imprisoned during the Franco dictatorship. Through an ongoing co-design process for a future immersive experience intended to educate younger generations, users identified personal objects associated with their imprisonment, such as a sweater they knitted or a book they read.

To support this process, users documented 12 objects using a custom web application, capturing photographs or videos and recording spoken or written descriptions. We then produced four 3D reconstructions of each object using different pipelines, varying both the input modality and the reconstruction method: text description, text combined with image description, a photo-to-3D pipeline, and a multi-image (video)-to-3D pipeline based on GS. Finally, we organised an evaluation session with former political prisoners and other project collectives (12 participants in total).

We describe the co-creation process, present the reconstruction pipelines, and report initial findings from the evaluation session. Our goal is to examine how participants perceive and compare these reconstruction approaches and to provide a preliminary answer to the following research questions:

RQ1: What reconstruction technique is preferred by participants?

RQ2: What factors, among realism, aesthetics, resemblance, and reminiscence, contribute to these preferences?

2 Related Work

2.1 Generative AI methods

The generation of 3D immersive content using generative AI has seen rapid progress across several interrelated research fronts. From a single image, multi-view diffusion approaches generate geometrically consistent renderings fused into a 3D mesh. Wonder3D [12] employs a cross-domain diffusion model that jointly produces normal maps and colour images across views, yielding accurate surfaces with high geometric consistency. ImageDream [23] extends this by introducing a multi-level image-prompt controller for both global layout control and fine-grained visual refinement. Plug-and-play methods such as Fancy123 [25] further address texture blurriness in Large Reconstruction Model pipelines through appearance and fidelity enhancement modules, achieving state-of-the-art results while remaining easily incorporated. Zero-shot generalisation is tackled by Deep Prior Assembly [28], which assembles pretrained vision and language model priors for pose estimation, scale alignment, and occlusion parsing without task-specific 3D training.

The high-fidelity asset generation was substantially advanced by Hunyuan3D 2.0 [26], a two-stage diffusion framework separating shape generation from texture synthesis, and extended by Hunyuan3D 2.5 [9], which scales geometry to 10B parameters and adds physically based rendering support. For novel view synthesis, Stable Virtual Camera [27] synthesises new viewpoints from sparse inputs without scene-specific optimisation, providing the multi-view inputs needed for GS [7] reconstruction from a single image. CAT3D [3] similarly generates internally consistent novel views fed into standard reconstruction pipelines, producing complete 3D scenes in approximately one minute.

2.2 Generative AI experiments

Generative AI is increasingly used to produce artistic and immersive content such as music [24], movies [2], and world-building systems in VR [19, 22]. However, audiences tend to distrust and dislike content once its AI origin is disclosed [1], and artists who co-create with AI are perceived as less authentic [14].

Evaluation of AI-generated material typically relies on Likert-based rating instruments measuring liking, beauty, novelty, and meaning [18], or dedicated aesthetic scales such as BeauVis [5]. Forced-choice paradigms have been applied to compare generative methods in synthesised videos [13], photorealistic object insertion [11], and neural style transfer [21], as well as to assess the visual quality of 3D content [4] and AI-based part representations [8].

When AI is used to recreate personal, real-world entities, evaluation must account for familiarity and memory-based expectations, not only surface aesthetics. Recognisability, perceived authenticity, and identity preservation can dominate preference, and highly aesthetic renderings are not necessarily the most preferred [6, 15]. Motivated by this, we investigate which AI-generated representation of a given personal object is preferred across alternative generations of the same entity.

3 User-content capture

To capture personal objects, the team created a user-friendly capture application so that the stakeholders could use their own devices to capture the media that will eventually generate the 3D objects.

3.1 Capture application

A web application called *Storybox* was created to enable users to capture, upload, and manage multimedia content directly from the browser in an easy-to-use manner, thereby transforming the immersive experience into a co-creation process with the stakeholders. Using a mobile phone or a tablet, users could capture images, videos, audio recordings, and written descriptions. This collected information serves as the raw data foundation for subsequent processing pipelines, where it can be transformed into richer digital representations, including 3D assets, GS reconstructions, and other advanced spatial or immersive formats. Therefore, *Storybox* enabled users to actively contribute content from their past, enriching the immersive experience.

3.2 Engagement of users

With the aim of creating a meaningful immersive experience from a past memory, researchers organised different sessions with the stakeholders to understand what could be valuable to add into the experience. After 2 co-design sessions, users remarked that personal objects linked to that past memory would give some legacy and give more truthfulness to the testimonies. These sessions helped identify the importance of adding personal objects as 3D reconstructions in the immersive experience.

Researchers presented the *Capture application* with instructions and a video tutorial so that they could capture objects (by photo or video) and provide a description of those objects (voice note or written; Figure 2). Lastly, 10 users (all female; nine were between 70 and 75 years old, and one was between 55 and 60 years old) captured different objects and photos using the application. All of them accepted the terms and conditions prior to participation.

4 3D Reconstruction Pipelines

Storybox integrates four reconstruction pipelines that transform user-captured media into 3D objects, combining generative AI models with classical reconstruction algorithms. Each pipeline takes a different form of input – text, image, or video – and produces one version of the reconstructed object per input (Figure 3).

Version 1 [text-to-3D] operates entirely from the user’s verbal or written description. ChatGPT [17] processes this description to extract physical/significance attributes, generating a JSON file. From this file, a concise descriptive sentence is produced and used as input to the pipeline. A 2D image is then synthesised via a Diffusion Transformer (DiT) architecture and passed to Hunyuan3D 2.0 [26] to generate a textured .gltf mesh.

Version 2 [text+-to-3D] enriches the text-based approach with visual context. In addition to the attribute JSON from Version 1, ChatGPT extracts visual attributes from the captured image or video (generating another JSON file), and BLIP [10] generates an image caption. These three inputs are combined by ChatGPT into a final description sentence, which feeds the same DiT + Hunyuan3D 2.0 pipeline as Version 1.

Version 3 [img-to-3D] bypasses text entirely, passing the captured image (or a frame extracted from video) directly to Hunyuan3D 2.0 [26]. Geometry is first generated via the ShapeVAE module, followed by texture synthesis via the Hunyuan3D-Paint architecture, producing a .gltf mesh.

Version 4 [Gaussian Splatting (GS)] reconstructs the object from multi-view video. Camera poses and an initial point cloud are estimated via COLMAP [20] using Structure-from-Motion, after which 3D GS [7] is applied to produce a .ply output. When only a single image is available, or when COLMAP fails, Stable Virtual Camera [27] first synthesises a set of multi-view images around the object; these serve as a substitute video input to the same pipeline. Be aware that the generative model hallucinates unseen regions, particularly the object’s back, which may not accurately represent the true geometry.

To facilitate reproducibility, the hardware requirements and execution times for the pipelines are the following: All methods were evaluated on a High-Performance Computing (HPC) cluster equipped with an NVIDIA A40 GPU (46 GiB VRAM) running CUDA 12.4. Approximate execution times are reported for the full text-to-3D pipeline, as it encompasses all sub-components: image-to-text, image-to-shape, and texture generation. Specifically, text-to-image synthesis completes in approximately 30 seconds, image-to-shape generation runs in under 1 minute, and texture generation takes approximately 5 minutes on average.

5 User Evaluation

5.1 Method

5.1.1 Participants. Twelve participants took part in the evaluation. Seven had previously participated in object capture, and five were additional women aged 34–55 years. All signed an informed consent form before completing the questionnaire and joining the recorded focus group.

5.1.2 Experimental protocol. Participants reviewed each object description with its original image or video, then viewed a frame of the original object alongside its four generated versions on the same screen (Figure 1 - User Evaluation).

All objects were completed in one session, beginning with a warm-up object used to explain the questionnaire. One participant that started in the first session continued in the second session, which first covered the unfinished objects before moving to the remaining ones.

5.1.3 Data collection. Participants rated each reconstruction relative to the original in terms of realism, aesthetics, resemblance, and reminiscence using a 5-point Likert-type scale (Table 1). They also selected their preferred version for each object.

5.2 Results

Figure 4 shows participants’ choices across reconstruction pipelines. The warm-up object was the *Pigeons Pillow*. GS received the most votes overall, although img-to-3D was preferred over GS for four objects and ranked as a close second for several others. Text-based pipelines were generally less preferred, except for the *Red Sweater*, where text+-to-3D performed reasonably well. For **RQ1**, GS was the most frequently preferred technique, likely because it was the

Figure 2: Steps followed by users in the Capture application (Storybox): (A) Users selected the language, introduced their name or ID, and provided consent to the terms and conditions. (B) Users captured a photo or video of the object. (C) Users described the object either using text or audio. (D) Users reviewed the result before uploading and could restart the process if needed.

Figure 3: Overview of the four processing pipelines. The figure shows four output versions generated from either an object description (written or transcribed) or an object capture (image or video). Translucent rectangles denote preprocessing steps, namely audio transcription, video generation from a single image, and frame extraction from video. Dashed lines represent prompts sent to ChatGPT, which include JSON files containing structured attributes. Version 1 (green) uses a text-to-3D method based on the description sentence generated by ChatGPT from the JSON file describing the physical/significant attributes. Version 2 (purple) uses a text+-to-3D method based on two JSON files extracted from the text and image inputs, (representing physical/significance attributes and visual attributes, respectively), and a BLIP generated caption. Version 3 (orange) uses an img-to-3D method based on either the input image or a frame extracted from the input video. Version 4 (blue) uses Gaussian Splatting based on either the input video or a video generated from a single image.

only non-generative pipeline and therefore preserved the original object’s appearance most faithfully. However, img-to-3D remained competitive and was occasionally preferred.

A closer look at each dimension (Figure 5) revealed 576 possible answers (12 participants × 12 objects × 4 pipelines). Of these, 27 were missing because of incomplete questionnaires and were not included in the analysis: 19 for *Pigeons Pillow*, 3 for *Book*, 2 for

Figure 4: Participant preferences for each object across reconstruction pipelines. Each row corresponds to an object and each column to a 3D reconstruction pipeline. The *None* column represents cases where participants either abstained or found none of the reconstructions satisfactory. Each vote has a total weight of 1; when n options were selected, the vote was distributed equally among them, assigning each a weight of $\frac{1}{n}$.

Dimension	Item	Scale
Realism	This version looks realistic	5-point Likert-type
Aesthetics	This version is aesthetically pleasing	
Resemblance	This version resembles the original	
Reminiscence	This version is reminiscent of the original object	
Preference	Preferred version (V1–V4)	Categorical

Table 1: Subjective evaluation questionnaire. Realism, aesthetics, resemblance, and reminiscence were rated on a 5-point Likert-type scale. Participants also selected their preferred version among the four, if any.

Baskets, and 3 for *Cook Book*. As a result, the figure does not include these missing responses.

Text-based pipelines consistently received the lowest scores (1 to 3.5), reflecting the difficulty of reconstructing identifiable objects from descriptions alone. They performed relatively better in realism and aesthetics than in resemblance and reminiscence, likely because

participant descriptions emphasised meaning over physical detail. In contrast, GS and *img-to-3D* achieved higher scores overall (3.5 to 5), particularly in resemblance and reminiscence.

The competition between *img-to-3D* and GS is nevertheless close and strongly object-dependent. GS tends to achieve higher scores in realism and resemblance for objects with well-defined, easily recognisable shapes, where it reaches the maximum rating of 5 in *Baskets*, *Baby Boots*, *Book*, and *Red Birds Pillow*. In contrast, *img-to-3D* scores higher for *Pigeons Pillow*, *Flowers Pillow*, *Knitting Balls*, and *Cook Book*. This latter is an interesting case, since the *img-to-3D* method scored higher in realism, but GS was preferred, likely due to better text readability. Contrarily, for *Blanket*, *img-to-3D* was preferred despite lower ratings, indicating that participants weighted criteria differently.

Deformable garments (e.g., *Brown Sweater*, *Red Sweater*) were challenging for all pipelines, yielding consistently lower scores, likely reflecting the inherent difficulty of reconstructing textured, deformable garments in 3D. For the *Brown Sweater* specifically, the

	...looks realistic				...is aesthetically pleasing				...resembles the original				...is reminiscent of the original object			
	text-to-3D	text+to-3D	img-to-3D	GS	text-to-3D	text+to-3D	img-to-3D	GS	text-to-3D	text+to-3D	img-to-3D	GS	text-to-3D	text+to-3D	img-to-3D	GS
Pigeons Pillow	1.1	1.7	4.5	3.3	2.7	2.2	4.2	2.8	1.3	2	4.3	2.8	1.5	1.6	4.3	3.4
Baskets	2.8	3.5	3.7	5	3.1	2.8	2.9	4.8	2.2	3.2	3.5	4.9	2	2.4	3.9	5
Book	1.5	1.6	4.3	4.9	2	1.1	3.4	4.8	1.5	1.8	4.6	4.9	1.8	1.8	4.7	5
Blanket	1.8	2.1	4.2	4.5	1.5	2.4	4.3	4.6	1.2	1.6	4.8	4.8	1.2	1.9	4.8	4.8
Flute	2.1	2.4	3.6	4.4	2.6	3.2	2.8	3.6	1.4	2.1	3.6	4.4	1.3	2.1	3.1	4.6
Baby Boots	1	3.2	3.6	4.9	1.2	3.6	3.3	4.6	1	2.7	3.2	5	1	2.6	3.2	5
Brown Sweater	2.3	2.3	3.3	2.8	2.7	2.5	2.8	2.4	1.8	1.2	2.8	2.9	1.9	1.3	3.2	3.8
Flowers Pillow	1.1	1.2	4.9	4.2	1.1	1.2	4.6	3.8	1	1	4.9	4.3	1.1	1	4.9	4.4
Knitting Balls	2	3.1	4.7	3.7	1.5	2.5	4	3.3	1.2	1.8	4.4	4.1	1	1.9	4.6	4.2
Red Birds Pillow	2.1	2.4	4.7	5	2.6	2.1	4.1	4.9	1.4	1.3	4.4	5	1.8	1.5	4.4	4.9
Cook Book	3.5	3.1	5	4.8	3.7	2.1	4.5	4.6	1.9	1.8	4.8	4.8	2.3	2	4.9	4.9
Red Sweater	2.4	3.2	4.2	3.8	2.2	3.6	3	3.3	1.2	3.1	4.7	4.3	1.3	3.2	4.5	4.3

Figure 5: Mean participant ratings per object and 3D reconstruction pipeline across four perceptual criteria: realism, aesthetic appeal, resemblance to the original, and reminiscence of the original object. Red borders highlight the highest-rated pipeline for each object.

GS version scores lower than img-to-3D on realism and aesthetics, yet it was still the preferred choice – a pattern explained by its higher ratings on resemblance and reminiscence.

Regarding **RQ2**, the perceptual ratings are broadly consistent with the observed preference votes. GS tends to lead on realism and resemblance, whereas img-to-3D is more competitive on aesthetic appeal, suggesting that generative methods may compensate for lower fidelity with visual attractiveness. Reminiscence follows a pattern similar to resemblance, implying that for participants with personal ties to the objects, recognisability and memory evocation tend to co-occur.

To quantify the relationship between these perceptual factors and participant preference, we fitted a logistic regression model predicting whether a version was selected or not from the four rated dimensions. The model converged successfully and showed a good fit (pseudo- $R^2 = 0.39$, likelihood ratio test: $p < 0.001$). Reminiscence ($\beta = 0.67$, $z = 2.60$, $p = 0.009$) and aesthetics ($\beta = 0.39$, $z = 2.62$, $p = 0.009$) were the only statistically significant predictors, while resemblance showed weak evidence of an effect ($\beta = 0.45$, $z = 1.89$, $p = 0.059$) and realism was not significant ($\beta = 0.08$, $p = 0.657$). The odds ratio for reminiscence (OR = 1.95) indicates that each one-point increase in reminiscence rating nearly doubled the odds of a version being preferred.

Overall, these results suggest that participant preference is driven less by perceived realism alone than by evocativeness and visual appeal, and to a lesser extent by resemblance. This is consistent with the broader goals of the project: in the context of an immersive experience about the lives of former political prisoners, the value of a reconstruction appears to depend not only on how realistic it looks, but also on how well it recalls the original object and the memories associated with it.

6 Conclusion

In this work-in-progress paper, we presented an end-to-end co-creation pipeline for reconstructing personal objects as 3D assets within an immersive experience based on the testimonies of former political prisoners during the Franco dictatorship. We described the capture app (*Storybox*), four reconstruction pipelines, and a preliminary participant evaluation with 12 participants. Overall, our results suggest that reconstruction quality in this context cannot be understood only in terms of technical fidelity. While visually faithful methods remain strong options for preserving the appearance of personal objects, more accessible generative approaches also show promise, particularly for non-expert participants.

These findings point to an important direction for accessible immersive content creation: reconstructed objects should be evaluated not only in terms of geometric or visual accuracy, but also through the subjective dimensions that matter in co-creation contexts. In such settings, the value of a reconstructed object may lie as much in its capacity to evoke memories as in its fidelity to the original.

This study has several limitations, including the small and heterogeneous sample, the diversity of the objects, the exploratory nature of the evaluation, and the difficulty all pipelines faced with deformable textured garments. Future work will involve a larger participant pool, a deeper analysis of the relationship between perceptual factors and preference, and the integration of the reconstructed objects into the final immersive experience to assess whether preferences shift when the objects are encountered in context rather than in isolation on a screen. We also plan to explore hybrid pipelines combining the fidelity of Gaussian Splatting with the aesthetic refinement of generative models.

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